

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Bekmuratova Aydana

**MANIFESTATION OF THE MULTIDIMENSIONALITY OF THE CONCEPT
FEAR IN ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS-EMOTIVES**

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
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MENTION
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